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EXPLORING INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE (ESL)

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Abstract: This paper explores the importance of English in today's world and innovative methodologies for teaching English as a second language (ESL). Relying on current research and best practices in language education, the article examines how new methodologies promote active language acquisition. Besides, it also gives explanations why traditional methods are not the best way to teach language learners.

Keywords: second language learning, traditional methods, CLT, TBLT.

In this global world, learning the English language is becoming more and more crucial as English has become the main used language in everywhere, from education to business trades. Over these past years, there have been many changes in the way English language education is designed and delivered around the world. In traditional teaching, memorizing and reciting grammar rules were the main methods of language teaching. Students just memorized the rule at home and recited it in a classroom, but it has a little effect in language acquisition. Teachers' duty at that time was assigning and listening to their students' recitations. Or another method was grammar-translation method, which mainly focused on translating texts from the English language to the native language. While this method can be useful for improving writing and reading skills, it often neglects communication skills. Although traditional teaching ways were used commonly by ESL educators, they had several drawbacks for students. For example, as traditional methods prioritized grammatical rules and translation skills, learners struggled to develop their speaking skills and they lacked confidence and fluency in communication. By acknowledging these shortcomings, teachers should embrace innovative technics that can help learners to acquire the language more perfectly.

In today's diverse and interconnected society, the importance of exploring innovative methods for teaching English as a second language (ESL) has become increasingly apparent than before. But why is that? Why traditional methods cannot address diverse needs of ESL learners? Well, there are given several reasons why innovative approaches are necessary in teaching English. Firstly, ESL learners come from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds which means, each of them has their unique set of challenges and learning preferences. Secondly, not all ESL classrooms have students who know the language perfectly. Students' proficiency levels range from beginners to advanced users and so educators need to provide support and challenges which are appropriate to each learners' level of proficiency. Moreover, each student has various personality which effects their language acquisition differently. Personality factors such as, introversion/extroversion, self-esteem, anxiety and risk-taking affect a student how much he or she acquires the language. Because of the factors above, language teachers need to avoid traditional ways and approach the language teaching in new ways.

The explanations and examples of modern language teaching methods.

As the language learning and teaching develop, everyone is realizing that communication is the main function of the language rather than its grammar and sentence structures. Grammar is definitely important as the language cannot be taught or learned without basic knowledge of them. However, still communication is vital when you learn a new language. One of the modern approaches to language teaching is the communicative language teaching method (CLT). This means that, nowadays teachers are focusing on students' active learning by using many contemporary techniques [1]. These techniques are:

- The use of smartphones or computers during lessons.
- The visual data usage during the lessons (videos, photos, PowerPoint).
- Training students to take notes during classes.
- Development of collaborative learning approaches.

When a teacher uses videos, photos and presentation slides to explain the lesson, students will more likely to memorize the lesson more. Furthermore, task-based language teaching (TBLT) is another method. In this, students work on different tasks which require them to use English to finish the challenge, such as solving a problem or completing a project. To use this method a teacher can divide students into groups and engage them in a debate on a controversial topic. Students research arguments, prepare speeches, and participate in a debate using English. This task helps students to build language proficiency in argumentation and critical thinking. Last interesting method is a flipped classroom. Students study English language outside of class by watching videos or completing various exercises and then, they will spend class time for discussions and other interactive activities.

In general, the evolution of language teaching methodologies underscores the imperative to adapt to the diverse needs and learning styles of ESL learners in today's globalized world. Traditional methods, rooted in rote memorization and translation, limit students' communication skills for navigating the complexities of a multilingual environment. By embracing innovative approaches such as Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), and flipped classrooms, educators can cultivate active language acquisition and empower students to engage confidently in real-world interactions. Through the integration of technology, collaborative learning, and practical tasks, learners are equipped with the tools and opportunities to develop fluency, critical thinking, and intercultural competence. As English continues to serve as a lingua franca in diverse spheres of life, the adoption of progressive teaching methodologies emerges as a crucial step towards

nurturing proficient and adaptable language learners prepared to thrive in an interconnected global community.

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